

ART - DESIGN GALLERIES AND CULTURAL TOURISM IN NIGERIA: A SYMBIOTIC NEXUS

By

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Abstract

Art and design galleries serve as vital hubs for preserving and showcasing Nigeria's diverse artistic and cultural heritage, attracting both local and international tourists. Galleries contribute to cultural tourism by offering unique and immersive experiences that highpoints the country's rich traditions, history, and contemporary artistic expressions. Cultural tourism also play major roles in promoting Nigeria's global cultural presence and generating economic benefits through e.g. increased visitor spending and job creation. Adopting a narrative review method, this paper explores this unique symbiotic relationship between galleries and cultural tourism in the Nigerian context, emphasising their collective impact on the nation's cultural and economic development. Key findings showed that art galleries promote Nigerian cultural heritage, attracting both local and international tourists, while cultural tourism enhances the visibility, patronage, and sustainability of galleries. These findings highlights a mutually beneficial nexus between cultural tourism and galleries. Key challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited marketing strategies, and the need for government support were also revealed. The findings suggest that strategic investments in art/design galleries and cultural tourism initiatives can significantly enhance Nigeria's cultural appeal and stimulate sustainable economic growth. The paper concludes with policy and practical recommendations for fostering a dynamic cultural tourism sector that leverages the strengths of Nigeria's art/design galleries.

Keywords: Arts, Art works, Culture, Design, Gallery

1. Introduction

What comes to mind when art is being mentioned is creativity, beauty, nature antiques, paintings, drawings, ornaments, fashion and of course sculptures, but many may not open their minds to a

great part of tourism; where galleries - collections of these creativity - can be opened to attract admirers, foreigners and therefore, improve socio-economic value of arts in Nigeria as well as in other parts of Africa. Art galleries can draw large numbers of tourists. The charm of art combined with its distinctive structural architecture often attracts tourists looking for cultural experiences (Franklin, 2018). As noted by Odji (2020), art is a vital part of culture. Hence, according to Franklin (2018), art tourism is a vital part of cultural tourism, within which galleries play major roles. Reiterating the assertions of Franklin (2018) and Odji (2020), Axelsen (2006) as cited in Herman et al. (2023) averred that galleries have the potential to improve tourist experience and inspire return visits through the provision of guided tours, special events and workshops.

Art, design and culture are indispensable components of human civilisation (Goodwin, 2006; Richta, 2018). Culture is regarded as the set of distinctive spiritual, material, intellectual and emotional features of society or a social group, and that it encompasses, in addition to art and literature, lifestyles, way of living together, value systems, traditions and beliefs (Naik et al., 2023; Odji, 2020). Tourism involves travelling from one destination to another by a person or group of persons for the purpose of leisure, social interaction and trade (Băbăţ et al., 2023). As noted by the World Tourism Organisation (WTO), tourism involves activities of anyone who visits another place or country for more than twenty-four hours, but less than 12 months, irrespective of the purpose of travel (Westcott & Anderson, 2021). Art and culture are important drivers of tourism i.e. cultural tourism, which embroils traveling for the purpose of experiencing the cultural heritage of other countries (Ertugruloglu et al., 2024; Naik et al., 2023).

Art galleries around the world act as stewards of cultural heritage by exhibiting works of art that capture the history, customs, and identity of a country. They are essential to the preservation and promotion of both indigenous and modern artistic creations in Nigeria, a nation rich in cultural diversity. The interaction between cultural tourism and art galleries creates a mutually beneficial nexus, as galleries provide a platform for showcasing art to both international and local tourists, while cultural tourism boosts the visibility and patronage of galleries. This study examines the symbiotic nexus between cultural tourism and art galleries in Nigeria, exploring how both sectors support each other's contribution to national development and growth.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The potential of art and design galleries in Nigeria as a major force behind cultural tourism is still underutilised, despite the country's rich cultural heritage. Many galleries in Nigeria suffer from low visitor engagement, little government assistance, and an obvious lack of funding, while Nigeria's cultural tourism sector grapples with issues such as insecurity, poor marketing and poor infrastructure (Adekunle, 2025; Amanawa, 2022; Ibidapo et al., 2019). This study aims to fill the knowledge gap regarding the ways in which cultural tourism and art galleries can be interwoven to strengthen their respective contributions to the country's economy and international cultural standing and sustainability.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

Broadly aimed at exploring the nexus between art/design galleries and cultural tourism in Nigeria, the objectives of the study included:

1. Exploring the role of art/design galleries in promoting cultural tourism in Nigeria.
2. Examining how cultural tourism enhances the growth and sustainability of galleries.
3. Analysing the social, economic and cultural benefits of the art - tourism nexus and;
4. Identifying opportunities and challenges in integrating art/design galleries with cultural tourism in Nigeria.

1.3 Methodology

The narrative review method was adopted for this study. This was intended to synthesise existing studies, scholarly works, and reports on the area of focus. This approach allowed for a comprehensive holistic of the art - cultural tourism nexus in Nigeria by analysing trends and case studies. With focus on Nigerian galleries and cultural sites, this study is significant for policymakers, tourism stakeholders, art and design gallery owners, and cultural enthusiasts by exploring how galleries attract cultural tourists and enhance Nigerian art and design. Findings were intended to inform policies and practices to strengthen their synergy. However, reliance on secondary data limited real-time statistics and firsthand visitor insights.

2.0 Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

2.1 Key Concepts

The study is grounded on three major concepts namely: art galleries, cultural tourism, and symbiotic relationship for development. Art galleries are curated spaces or institutions dedicated to the exhibition, promotion, preservation of artistic expressions such as paintings, multimedia art forms, and sculptural pieces serving as commercial and cultural hubs within the creative industry (Max, 2024; Pioli, 2024). Cultural tourism thrives on the exploration, engagement with and appreciation of the cultural assets of a country, such as its artistic heritage, traditional festivals, historical sites, and indigenous lifestyles, which contribute to both economic growth and cultural sustainability (Ezenagu, 2020; Odji, 2020; Smith, 2015). The symbiotic relationship in cultural development refers to the mutually reinforcing interaction between interconnected sectors — such as cultural tourism and art galleries — where collaboration fosters cultural sustainability, economic viability, and enhanced global visibility. Art galleries, through their immersive experiences, contribute to cultural tourism, enhancing visibility and financial sustainability, and fostering cultural preservation, economic development, and a globally competitive creative industry.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on three theories namely the Cultural Capital Theory (CCT), the Creative Economy Framework (CEF) and the Destination Image Theory (DIT). This interdisciplinary theoretical base that sheds light on the intersection between cultural tourism and art galleries. Pierre Bourdieu's CCT posits that cultural assets, including artistic heritage, function as a form of capital that enhances social mobility, economic opportunities, and national identity (Huang, 2019). Art galleries, as repositories of cultural capital, are germane in influencing economic structures

and societal value systems. The CEF, grounded in the principles of culture-driven economic development, highlights the transformative role of innovation, creativity and cultural assets in economic diversification (Gurgu et al., 2024; Mubarok et al., 2024; Zou et al., 2025). In the light of the CEF, cultural tourism and art galleries are positioned as integral elements of a broader creative economy, which underscores their prospects in global competitiveness, job creation, and ultimately national development.

The DIT emphasises the importance of perception in tourism, asserting that tourists are drawn to destinations based on the image constructed via media portrayal, artistic representation, media portrayal and especially cultural branding (Arismayanti et al., 2024; Zolak, 2024). This context of use of the DIT is closely related to the structural relationship of destination image, branding, etc. of the tourist-satisfaction-model (Arismayanti et al., 2024). As can be deduced from studies such as Foster et al. (2020), Odji (2020) and Stylianou-Lambert (2011), galleries contribute to shaping the cultural identity of a destination, influencing tourist engagement and visitation patterns. This study integrates these theories to understand the nexus between cultural tourism and art/design galleries, emphasising their significant influence on cultural sustainability as well as economic growth in the Nigerian context.

3. Overview of Art Galleries in Nigeria

3.1 History and Evolution of Art Galleries in Nigeria

Art galleries in Nigeria have a rich history dating back to the colonial era, where they showcased traditional and contemporary African art. Artists expressed indigenous culture in the forms of masks, sculptures, textiles, and paintings. After Nigeria gained independence in 1960, the art scene expanded, with more artists experimenting with various styles and mediums. Over time, art galleries have evolved, embracing more digital and modern art while preserving traditional expressions. There are studies such as Odji (2020) that emphasise the need to sustain the African expressions in African arts and culture. There was also the rise of contemporary Nigerian artists fueling the establishment of more art spaces that cater for diverse artistic styles. Today, art galleries serve as platforms for both emerging and established artists.

3.2 Classifications of Art Galleries in Nigeria

Nigeria has a diverse range of art galleries distributed in various parts of the country, although they seem to be more concentrated in some regions than in others. Such galleries include the Nike Art Gallery in Lagos, which houses over 8,000 Nigerian artworks. The National Gallery of Modern Art in Lagos showcases contemporary pieces from renowned artists like Bruce Onobrakpeya and Ben Osawe. The Red Door Gallery in Victoria Island specialises in African contemporary art, offering a modern aesthetic experience. The Ovuomaroro Studio and Gallery, one of Lagos' oldest, remains a significant cultural hub. Beyond the shores of prominent states such as Lagos, Nigeria's cultural scenery is enriched by notable art spaces in other cities like Osogbo and Abuja. For example, the Genesis Art Gallery, which was founded in 1990 and moved to Osogbo, Osun State, in 1996, is one of the many influential galleries in the country. The Thought Pyramid Art Centre in Abuja is another example of the country's changing artistic narrative, which combines modern

and traditional art forms to showcase Nigerian talents and culture. The Museum of West African Art (MOWAA) in Benin is another prominent gallery in the country.

Largely, art galleries in Nigeria may be viewed in the light of three broad categories namely: public galleries, private galleries, and contemporary spaces. Public galleries, like the National Gallery of Art, are government-owned institutions that showcase and preserve Nigerian artistic heritage. Private galleries, like Nike Art Gallery in Lagos, largely support emerging artists, while striving to preserve Nigerian and African artistic skills and expressions. Contemporary spaces combine traditional exhibitions with multimedia and digital art. There is also the more traditional cultural spaces or locations such as the Osun-Osogbo Sacred Grove (UNESCO, 2025).

Galleries in Nigeria may also be viewed in terms of locations – urban or rural. The contrast between urban and rural art galleries in Nigeria offers tourists diverse experiences. The urban galleries are often larger and more internationally connected. These spaces frequently host high-profile exhibitions and events. On the other hand, rural galleries are often smaller but equally significant. These galleries provide intimate insights into local artistic traditions and community life. This rural-urban dichotomy enriches Nigeria's cultural tourism offering, allowing visitors to experience both contemporary trends, grassroots creativity and diverse cultural experiences. Urban galleries, often located in bustling city centers, tend to focus on contemporary art and international collaborations. The Art Twenty One gallery in Lagos, for example, regularly hosts exhibitions featuring both Nigerian and international artists, creating a cosmopolitan atmosphere (Art Twenty One, 2024). Rural galleries, on the other hand, often emphasise local crafts and traditional art forms. The Osun-Osogbo Sacred Grove, a UNESCO World Heritage site and a major cultural tourism destination, combines natural beauty with traditional Yoruba art, offering visitors a unique, immersive cultural experience away from the urban hustle (Oyefeso, 2020; UNESCO, 2025).

Plate 1: The Osun-Osogbo Sacred Grove (Oyefeso, 2020).

3.3 Art-Design Galleries and Cultural Preservation

As stewards of artistic heritage, art galleries aid in the conservation, documentation, and display of works of art that represent a community's history, values, and traditions (Banda et al., 2024; Mekonnen et al., 2022). Since it gives artists and or designers a place to display their work, galleries guarantee that a variety of cultural narratives are represented and available to the public, which in turn promotes a greater understanding and appreciation of other cultures, fostering social cohesion and intercultural dialogue. Besides the aforementioned, art galleries frequently participate in educational programs, including workshops, lectures, and publications, that spread knowledge about various art forms and their cultural significance, helping to transmit intangible cultural heritage, making sure that traditional methods, tales, and symbols are passed down to future generations (Achille & Fiorillo, 2022; Li, 2024; Shakya & Vagnarelli, 2024; Xia et al., 2024). In the Nigerian context, galleries in the country, through the aforementioned means/mediums and art forms, have overtime helped in preserving and promoting Nigerian culture. For example, the Nigerian National Gallery of Art, MOWAA, and Yemisi Shyllon Museum of Art have been key institutions in promoting and preserving the country's cultural heritage. The Nigerian National Gallery of Art, established in 1993, collects, conserves, and promotes Nigerian art through exhibitions and educational programs. The Yemisi Shyllon Museum of Art, inaugurated in 2019, houses a diverse collection of artworks, exploring themes relevant to Nigerian society. MOWAA in Benin City aims to provide advanced facilities for the preservation and study of West African art, challenging narratives that question Africa's capacity to conserve its own heritage.

Generally, galleries serve as pivotal hubs in the development of cultural tourism. They act as cultural ambassadors, showcasing a region's artistic heritage and contemporary creativity (Jiawei & Sangiamvibool, 2025; Walden, 2019). Through offering visitors a platform to engage with local art, galleries contribute to a deeper understanding and appreciation of the host culture. According to Rajan (2024), art contributes to the preservation of cultural heritage by safeguarding and showcasing art collections.

3.3.1 Beyond Cultural Preservation

Beyond their cultural significance, art galleries contribute substantially to the society in terms of economic growth, tourism, and such like.

Art Galleries as Economic prospect

Contrary to the often-overlooked perception of art galleries as mere aesthetic spaces, these cultural institutions are potent drivers of economic growth (Budney, 2018). In the Nigerian context, art galleries emerge as significant opportunities for economic diversification and stimulation. By serving as platforms for showcasing local talent, attracting tourists, and fostering cultural exchange, art galleries contribute substantially to a region's economic vitality.

At the core of an art gallery's economic impact is its role as a job creator. They create employment opportunities for artists, curators, and support staff (Baverstock, 2010; Fillis et al., 2022; Thom, 2015). Galleries employ a range of professionals including curators, art handlers, marketing specialists, and administrative staff. Besides the obvious, the ancillary services required to support the gallery, such as framing, installation, and security, also create additional employment opportunities (Štefko & Kraj, 2013). Galleries also generate revenue through ticket sales, merchandise, and cafe operations.

However, the economic impact of galleries extends beyond these direct revenue sources. When visitors travel to see art galleries, they often spend money on accommodation, transportation, and dining, stimulating local businesses. This multiplier effect can be substantial, especially in regions with a thriving art scene like Lagos. In essence, the influx of tourists visiting art galleries also benefits related industries such as transportation, hospitality, and retail.

Art Galleries as Platforms for Entrepreneurship

Art galleries can serve as incubators for entrepreneurial ventures. Artists can use galleries to sell their work directly to consumers, bypassing traditional retail channels. In addition, galleries can collaborate with other businesses, such as fashion designers or interior decorators, to create unique products and services (Nogare & Murzyn-Kupisz, 2022; Thom, 2015; Zelenskaya et al., 2022).

Art Galleries as Platforms for Innovations

According to Nogare & Murzyn-Kupisz (2022), art and design galleries aid in fostering innovation especially through engagement with the cultural and creative industries. While this has not been sufficiently given the deserving scholarly attention in Nigeria, it is yet a major contributory point of galleries to the Nigerian system.

Art Galleries and Cultural Tourism in Nigeria

Nigeria, with its rich cultural heritage and vibrant art scene, has emerged as a significant player in the global art market. Art galleries across the country serve as important conduits for cultural tourism, offering visitors a unique glimpse into the nation's artistic soul (Castellote & Okwuosa, 2020). Art galleries contribute significantly to Nigeria's cultural tourism economy through tourist attraction, artist promotion and cultural preservation. According to Edewor et al. (2023), the contribution of art galleries to Nigeria's cultural tourism economy is substantial. Art galleries in Nigeria are vital for driving tourism, promoting artists, and preserving cultural heritage. They attract both domestic and international visitors, contributing to local economies through accommodation, transport, and local businesses. They also showcase Nigerian artists, providing them with economic opportunities and global exposure. Art galleries also preserve Nigeria's rich cultural heritage by displaying traditional and contemporary artworks, which in turn fuels tourism by allowing visitors to experience the country's artistic and historical legacy. Existing statistics indicated that, between the first quarter of 2020 (Q1) and the second quarter of 2022 (Q2), the arts, entertainment, and recreation sector contributed an average of 0.23% to Nigeria's GDP (Statista, 2022), with a significant portion attributed to gallery visits and art tourism. According to Domingues & Almeida (2024), art-related tourism contributed approximately 2.5% to the country's GDP, with galleries playing a significant role in this trajectory. If properly enhanced and harnessed, art galleries would create more jobs, stimulate local economies, and attract foreign investments.

3.3.2 Nigeria's Contemporary Art Scene

Nigeria's contemporary art galleries have become powerful magnets for cultural tourists, showcasing the country's dynamic and evolving artistic expression. These spaces, particularly in urban centers like Lagos and Abuja, serve as platforms for emerging and established artists to display their work to a global audience, as such, Art Galleries as Custodians of Nigerian Heritage would serve an avenue of Preserving Nigeria rich and diversified Tradition. According to Ogunbiyi (2018), while contemporary art thrives, galleries also play a crucial role in preserving and promoting traditional Nigerian art forms. Many galleries curate exhibitions that showcase ancient techniques and motifs, educating visitors about Nigeria's rich artistic heritage. In the words of Ademola Adesina, art historian at the University of Lagos, Nigeria:

"Art galleries are not just spaces for display; they are living museums that bridge the past and present of Nigerian culture," (Dr. Ademola Adesina).

3.4 Preserving Traditional Nigerian Art

While embracing modernity, Nigerian art galleries play a crucial role in preserving and promoting traditional art forms. The National Museum in Lagos and the Odinani Museum in Nri showcase ancient artifacts, traditional sculptures, and historical pieces that offer insights into Nigeria's rich cultural past (Adams, 2002; Kohol & Adeleke, 2023). Galleries such as these serve as educational hubs, allowing both international and local visitors to explore the various art forms emanating from Nigeria such as the Uli art forms among the Igbos, the intricate beadwork of the Yorubas, the bronze castings of Benin, and the terracotta sculptures of Nok, etc. By preserving these traditional

art forms, galleries contribute significantly to cultural tourism, attracting those interested in African heritage and history.

3.5 Challenges Faced by Nigerian Galleries

Nigerian art galleries encounter many obstacles that impede their expansion and long-term viability. Lack of government funding is a significant problem that restricts galleries' capacity to grow, hold exhibitions, and conserve artwork. Additionally, low local patronage lowers sales and revenue for artists and gallery owners, frequently as a result of a lack of appreciation for art and financial limitations. Nigerian artists' limited international recognition further limits their chances of receiving international exposure because many galleries find it difficult to establish connections with foreign museums, collectors, and art fairs. The quality of art exhibits and visitor experiences are impacted by poor infrastructure, which includes unstable electricity and insufficient exhibition spaces. Investors and tourists are also deterred from participating in the art industry by security concerns. Also, galleries struggle to thrive in Nigeria due to poor marketing plans and the high price of art supplies, versus the economic capacity (i.e. purchasing power) of many Nigerians. Nigerian art galleries will continue to struggle to realise their full potential in the presence of these challenges.

4. Cultural Tourism in Nigeria and Accruing Challenges

4.1 Understanding Cultural Tourism

Cultural tourism in Nigeria is a significant industry that attracts both local and international visitors to explore the country's rich cultural heritage. Nigeria offers a rich scene of cultural attractions stretching from festivals to historical sites. Examples include festivals such as the Osun-Osogbo Festival and Argungu Fishing Festival, as well as historical sites like the Nok Terracotta and Benin Bronzes and Royal Palace of Benin (Asifat et al., 2025; Atairu, 2024; Franke, 2024; Onihunwa et al., 2023). Cultural tourism, through art galleries and museums, showcase traditional and contemporary Nigerian art, preserving the nation's identity and providing economic opportunities for local artists. Cultural tourism also fosters appreciation for Nigeria's diverse ethnic groups, crafts, and traditions, strengthening national unity. The sector generates revenue and creates jobs in hospitality, transport, and cultural industries.

4.2 Challenges Faced in the Cultural Tourism Sector in Nigeria

Cultural tourism in Nigeria holds immense potential, yet it faces several significant challenges that significantly hinder its full potentials and effective development, ranging from security issues to poor funding or inadequate investment in the sector (Egbejule, 2024; Eyisi et al., 2023; Onyima, 2016).

Inadequate infrastructure remains one of the most pressing issues hindering the development of cultural tourism in Nigeria (Eyisi et al., 2023; Odeku, 2020). Many tourist locations are less appealing to both domestic and foreign tourists because they lack basic amenities like dependable transportation systems, well-paved access roads, and first-rate lodging. Traveling to heritage sites is challenging due to poor road conditions and a lack of public transportation options, which lowers

the number of tourists. Furthermore, the lack of contemporary lodging options, dining options, and recreational amenities deters extended visits and reduces the potential economic gains from tourism. Nigeria's incapacity to offer a smooth travel experience has resulted in fewer international visitors than other African countries, despite the country's abundant natural and cultural attractions. Nigeria's appeal as a top destination for cultural tourism is further diminished by this infrastructure deficit, which is closely linked to insufficient government investment and poor urban planning (Egbejule, 2024). Without major infrastructure upgrades, the industry's potential may largely remain unrealised, limiting the contribution of (cultural) tourism to the economic growth of the country.

Due to the nation's struggles with crime, regional conflicts, and political instability, security concerns also significantly contribute to the deterrence of potential tourists (Egbejule, 2024; Mshelia et al., 2024). Due to reports of kidnappings, armed attacks, and general insecurity in some areas, many tourists believe Nigeria to be unsafe, deterring both international and local tourists (Egbejule, 2024). The issue is made worse by the absence of adequate security measures surrounding tourist attractions and cultural heritage sites, which leaves tourists vulnerable and less inclined to experience Nigeria's diverse cultural offerings (Mshelia et al., 2024; Muoneke, 2024).

However, there are also more subtle challenges such as inadequate marketing tactics, which have kept Nigeria from becoming known globally as a top destination for cultural tourism. There is little cooperation with foreign travel agencies to draw tourists, and the nation's cultural assets are not adequately promoted on international platforms. Moreover, historical sites, museums, and indigenous customs have been neglected as a result of the low level of investment in cultural preservation, which has gradually reduced their allure (Nilson & Thorell, 2018; Nomishan et al., 2021; Onyima, 2016). Many heritage sites deteriorate without adequate care, wiping out significant aspects of Nigeria's cultural identity.

According to Odji (2020), factors such as predatory acculturation, excessive drive for modernisation, corruption and importation of technological, social and economic models all contribute to the erosion of culture in Nigeria and in Africa at large, with significant impact on the cultural tourism sector. Therefore, To fully derive the cultural and economic benefits of tourism, Nigeria must address these identified issues.

5. The Symbiotic Nexus between Art Galleries and Cultural Tourism

5.1 A Mutually Beneficial Art-Tourism Synergy

As already established, art and design galleries are significant drivers of cultural tourism. For instance, they offer visitors immersive experiences through workshops, exhibitions, and interactive sessions with artists (Asta et al., 2024; BealeGareth et al., 2022; Pan, 2021). These cultural spaces function as cultural centers where visitors can interact with Nigeria's rich artistic legacy, which includes everything from modern installations that showcase the country's changing creative scene to traditional sculptures, paintings, and other art forms. Art galleries are important locations that highlight both historical and contemporary Nigerian artistry since many tourists are looking for

genuine cultural experiences, which sometimes get lost in excessive acculturation and modernisation drives as noted by Odji (2020).

5.2 Economic and Social Benefits of the Art-Tourism Synergy

Nigeria benefits economically and socially from the synergy between art and tourism, especially when it comes to the creation of jobs in the tourism and creative industries (Sandhya et al., 2024; Scott, 2024). While the tourism industry gains from the increased demand for local businesses, transportation, and hospitality, art and design galleries, museums, and cultural festivals also generate jobs for artists, designers, curators, tour guides, artisans, and event planners. In addition to strengthening regional economies, this nexus gives creative workers a steady source of income. Moreover, by drawing tourists from abroad who are interested in Nigerian art and design, history, and customs, art-tourism promotes cultural exchange and heritage promotion. While local artists, designers and communities gain from exposure to international artistic/design trends and perspectives, according to the Nigeria Embassy in Berlin (2025), tourists who visit galleries and attend art festivals acquire a deeper understanding of Nigeria's diverse cultures. Nigerian art's increasing international recognition also enhances the nation's standing as a major force in the creative sector and enhances its reputation as a global cultural powerhouse. As Nigerian art becomes more well-known, it boosts national pride, draws in foreign capital, and promotes diplomatic and commercial partnerships through cultural diplomacy. In the end, this vibrant interaction between art and tourism supports both the preservation of Nigeria's rich cultural legacy and sustainable economic growth.

5.3 Challenges and Opportunities in the Art-Tourism Synergy in Nigeria

Nigeria faces a number of obstacles in integrating art galleries and cultural tourism, chief among them being inadequate policy implementation and a lack of knowledge about the opportunities for cultural tourism (Mfon, 2017; Omojola & Yacim, 2024). Although there are policies and laws governing cultural tourism, their efficacy is hampered by lax enforcement and uneven government support, which leaves many galleries and cultural institutions without the capital, facilities, or marketing support they need to draw in both domestic and foreign tourists (Adetola et al., 2024; Ayibadeinyefa, 2011). Furthermore, many Nigerians are unable to fully interact with galleries due to a general lack of knowledge/awareness about the cultural and economic advantages of art, design or cultural tourism, which results in low domestic patronage (Mfon, 2017). Nonetheless, this industry offers a lot of room for expansion and sustainability.

Virtual gallery tours and other forms of digitalisation, although yet very minimally adopted, provide a means of reaching a wider audience, enabling visitors from around the world to view Nigerian art and design from a distance and potentially boosting engagement and sales. The Yemisi Shyllon Museum, for example, have tapped into this sphere of the nexus with virtual tours enabled as at the time of this study (Yemisi Shyllon Museum, 2025).

Plate 2: A screenshot from the Yemisi Shyllon Museum virtual space (Yemisi Shyllon Museum, 2025).

In addition to this, improved cooperation between the private and public sectors can supply capital, infrastructure, and marketing assistance to increase the awareness and sustainability of art tourism. Public-private partnerships may result in projects like international exhibitions, art residency programs, and better management of heritage sites if well implemented, all of which would strengthen Nigeria's standing as a destination for cultural tourism and guarantee the long-term viability of art galleries.

5.4 Case Studies of Successful Art-Tourism Collaborations in Nigeria

To a considerable extent, the art –and- tourism nexus in Nigeria has impacted both on cultural tourism, attracting both international and local tourists while maintaining artistic traditions. Aside from the Yemisi Shyllon Museum, some Nigerian cases (both private and public) stand out in this respect, including: the Nike Art Gallery, the National gallery, the Ake and Benin Arts as well as the Osogbo Art Movement.

Case 1: The Nike Art Gallery

Nike Art Gallery, founded by Chief Nike Davies-Okundaye, is a renowned West African art gallery with branches in Lagos, Abuja, Oshogbo, and Ogidi (Madichie & Hinson, 2022; Ogundare et al., 2024). The gallery houses thousands of artworks, including paintings, sculptures, textiles, and beadwork. It partners with tourism bodies like the Nigerian Tourism Development Corporation and Lagos State Tourism Board to promote Nigeria's artistic heritage. Collaborations include curated tour packages, art workshops on traditional crafts, and government-endorsed cultural promotions at international tourism expos. This significantly boosts art tourism, generates revenue

for local artists, and fosters cultural exchange with foreign artists, strengthening Nigeria's global artistic presence.

Case 2: The National Gallery

The National Gallery of Art, a parastatal under Nigeria's Federal Ministry of Tourism, Culture, and Orientation, has been a significant promoter of art and culture since its inception as a government parastatal in line with the 1988 Cultural Policy requirements of Nigeria, and formalised through Decree No. 86 of 1993. Its details are spelt out in the National Gallery of Art Act (1993). It organises free annual art exhibitions e.g. during the National Iwa Ji festival or Children's Day celebrations, showcasing Nigerian art, attracting tourists, and preserving cultural heritage. However, challenges like limited infrastructure, insufficient funding, and low public awareness hinder its full potential.

Case 3: The National War Museum

The National War Museum in Umuahia is a cultural and historical institution that preserves the Nigerian Civil War legacy and celebrates the Igbo people's art and heritage (Emeafor & Onyemechalu, 2021; Onuoha, 2016). It features wartime relics, traditional artifacts, and contemporary art and designs, providing visitors with a significant understanding of historical conflicts in Nigeria and artistic expressions. The museum's tourism experience combines history and creativity, attracting historians, artists, designers, and tourists. Through exhibitions, guided tours, and interactive installations, the museum promotes local craftsmanship and preserves heritage, making it a vital landmark for cultural tourism in Eastern Nigeria, while yet promoting itself as a gallery of art/design.

Case 4: The Osogbo Art Movement

The Osogbo Art Movement, a cultural movement in Nigeria, emerged in the 1960s under German artists Ulli Beier and Susanne Wenger (Weise, 2016). It influenced artists like Twin Seven Seven, Jimoh Buraimoh, and Rufus Ogundele, who drew from Yoruba mythology (Indigo Arts Gallery, 2024; Weise, 2016). The movement led to the recognition of the Osun-Osogbo Sacred Grove. Osogbo's efforts to preserve its artistic legacy include exhibitions, heritage conservation, and international collaborations. Institutions like the Nike Centre for Art and Culture in Osogbo promote the movement through art residencies and workshops.

Case 5: The Benin Art and Revival of Tourism

Benin City, the historical capital of the Edo Kingdom, is known for its Benin Bronzes, 13th-century African artworks (Eyo, 2014; Plankensteiner, 2007). Despite colonial-era looting, efforts to revive the artifacts are ongoing. The Benin City National Museum preserves these artifacts and collaborates with tourism organisations to attract visitors. MOWAA in Edo state restores Benin's cultural legacy and attracts global tourists (Merriman, 2024; MOWAA, 2023). The annual Edo Festival and Cultural Expo promotes cultural tourism by combining traditional performances with art exhibitions (Edosomwan, 2010; Eweka, 2015). Heritage repatriation efforts have revived global

interest in Benin art, while museums and cultural festivals attract visitors and contribute to Edo State's economy.

While challenges yet exist, these case studies are proofs that the art-tourism nexus is, not just possible but also, economically and culturally beneficial, both profiting the galleries and aiding cultural sustainability.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

The study explored the nexus between art galleries and cultural tourism in Nigeria, highlighting their mutual benefits in cultural preservation, economic growth and global recognition. Key findings showed that art galleries promote Nigerian cultural heritage, attracting both local and international tourists, while cultural tourism enhances the visibility, patronage, and sustainability of galleries. These findings highlights a mutually beneficial nexus between cultural tourism and galleries, and is in consonance with the assertions of similar studies such as Scott (2024). The growing global interest in African art, digital technologies, and increased government-private sector collaboration present opportunities for strengthening this relationship. However, challenges like poor infrastructure, inadequate funding, limited marketing, and security concerns hinder their full potential. Addressing these challenges can position Nigeria as a leading cultural tourism destination and also enhance the economic viability of its art and design sector.

Based on the key findings, the following practical and policy recommendations are proposed:

- 1) Strengthening partnerships between art galleries, the Nigerian Tourism Development Authority, and private tourism operators to include art galleries in international and national tour packages.
- 2) Increased government investment in cultural infrastructure to enhance visitor experience and attract tourists.
- 3) Enhanced global promotion and marketing of Nigerian art through digital campaigns, collaborations with global art institutions and international exhibitions.
- 4) Integration of digital technology and design of virtual tours for the purpose of expanding global reach and providing access to those unable to visit physical galleries.
- 5) Improved security measures for cultural tourism sites to ensure a safe environment for tourists. Campaigns may be run to assure tourists of their safety during visits/tours.
- 6) Workshops, training programs, and financial support for artists, creative designers, curators, and cultural managers for the purpose of enhancing their skills and promoting sustainable practices.
- 7) Development of effective policies to regulate and support the integration of art galleries with cultural tourism.

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